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Application of the Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) for the Wadden Sea World Heritage property

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Executive summary

Climate change is the fastest growing global threat to World Heritage. Many World Heritage properties around the world are already experiencing significant negative impacts, damage and degradation. The Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) is a methodology to rapidly assess climate change risk to World Heritage properties (natural, cultural, or mixed) by expert appraisal and based on the best-available climate science.

From 2019-2021, the CVI method was piloted in the Wadden Sea World Heritage property. The two phases of the CVI were conducted in two separate workshops of key international Wadden Sea experts representing different scientific and academic sectors: Phase 1 centred around the Outstanding Universal Value (OUV) of the property, held in Hamburg, Germany (10-11 February 2020); Phase 2 on Community Vulnerability was held online (16-17 February 2021). This report summarises outcomes from both workshops.

The three key climate stressors identified to have the greatest impact on the Wadden Sea OUV were:

- Temperature trend (air and/or water);
- Extreme temperature events; and
- Sea level rise.

These were consistent across the two timeframes considered (ca. 2050 and ca. 2100) using a high-emissions climate scenario (RCP8.5), which represents the most likely consequence of current international policies linked to greenhouse gas emissions. **OUV Vulnerability was assessed as High** (the highest category) for both timeframes. Whilst the vulnerability associated with the two temperature-related climate stressors was assessed as High in both timeframes, the vulnerability to impacts from Sea level rise escalated from Low in ca. 2050 to High in ca. 2100. Collectively and for both timeframes, there is potential for major loss or substantial alteration of the majority of the attributes that convey the OUV.

The assessment of Community Vulnerability was undertaken as a single evaluation across the entire property, which provided some challenges due to the high complexity of the Wadden Sea and the diversity of its associated community. Workshop participants agreed on qualitative conclusions, such as a de-coupling of economic sectors from the property values, and open questions, including the need to systematically identify research questions and to further analyse and assess the interrelations between economic, social and cultural values and the OUV under climate change influence.

The view through the lens of World Heritage and its OUV proved very helpful for management considerations to systematically safeguard the OUV of the site. Results of the CVI process fed into “The SIMP Integrated Management Plan for ONE Wadden Sea World Heritage”, which was being developed in parallel with the CVI application. Findings further supported the identification of management goals for the World Heritage site in a draft Ministerial Declaration for the 2022-2026 period of the Trilateral Cooperation on the

Protection of the Wadden Sea and served as input for the 3rd cycle of the UNESCO periodic reporting.

Resumé

Dansk

Klimaforandringer er den hurtigst voksende, globale trussel mod verdensarven. Flere af verdens verdensarvssteder gennemgår allerede markante, negative påvirkninger, skader og nedbrydning. The Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) er en metode til hurtigt at vurdere risikoen for klimaforandringer mod verdensarvssteder (både naturlige, kulturelle eller begge dele) gennem ekspertvurderinger og er baseret på den nyeste viden inden for klimavidenskab.

I perioden 2019-2021 blev CVI-metoden afprøvet i Verdensarv Vadehavet. Metodens to faser blev gennemført på to individuelle workshops af centrale, internationale Vadehavseksperter, som repræsenterer forskellige, videnskabelige og akademiske sektorer: Fase 1 omhandlede verdensarvsstedets Outstanding Universal Value (OUV) og blev afholdt i Hamborg, Tyskland den 10. – 11. februar 2020. Fase 2 omhandlede Community Vulnerability og blev afholdt online den 16. – 17. februar 2021. Denne rapport opsummerer resultaterne fra begge workshops.

De tre centrale klimastressfaktorer, der blev identificeret til at have den største påvirkning på Vadehavets OUV var:

- Tendenser i temperaturer (luft og/eller vand);
- Ekstreme temperaturudsving; og
- Havniveaustigninger.

Disse faktorer var konsistente på tværs af de to undersøgte perioder (ca. 2050 og ca. 2100) ved brug af et klimascenarie (RCP8.5), som repræsenterer den mest sandsynlige konsekvens af nuværende, internationale politikker, der er knyttet til drivhusgasemissioner. **OUV Vulnerability blev vurderet som værende Høj** (den højeste kategori) i begge perioder. Mens sårbarheden forbundet med de to temperaturrelaterede klimastressfaktorer blev vurderet som høj i begge tidsrammer, eskalerede sårbarheden over for påvirkninger fra havniveaustigning fra Lav i ca. 2050 til Høj i ca. 2100. Samlet set, og for begge perioder, er der sandsynlighed for større tab eller væsentlige ændringer af størstedelen af de egenskaber, der formidler OUV.

Vurderingen af Community Vulnerability blev foretaget som en enkelt evaluering på tværs af hele verdensarvsstedet, hvilket gav nogle udfordringer grundet Vadehavets høje kompleksitet og mangfoldigheden af dets tilknyttede samfund. Workshopdeltagerne blev enige om kvalitative konklusioner, såsom en afkobling af økonomiske sektorer fra ejendomsværdierne, og åbne spørgsmål, herunder behovet for systematisk at identificere forskningsspørgsmål og for yderligere at analysere og vurdere sammenhængen mellem økonomiske, sociale og

kulturelle værdier og OUV under indflydelse af klimaforandringer. Workshopen belyste behovet for systematisk at identificere forskningsspørgsmål og yderligere analysere og vurdere sammenhængen mellem økonomiske, sociale og kulturelle værdier og OUV under indflydelse af klimaforandringer.

Fremtiden for verdensarven og dens OUV viste sig ganske lys i de forvaltningsmæssige overvejelser for systematisk at sikre stedets OUV. Resultaterne af CVI-processen indgår i ”The SIMP Integrated Management Plan for ONE Wadden Sea World Heritage”, som blev udviklet sideløbende med CVI-applikationen. Resultaterne understøttede yderligere identifikationen af verdensarvsstedets forvaltningsmål i et udkast til ministererklæringen for perioden 2022-2026 for det trilaterale samarbejde om beskyttelse af Vadehavet og tjente som input til 3. cyklus af UNESCO's periodiske rapportering.

Zusammenfassung

Deutsch

Der Klimawandel ist die am schnellsten wachsende globale Bedrohung für das Welterbe. Viele Welterbestätten auf der ganzen Welt sind bereits mit erheblichen negativen Auswirkungen, Schäden und Beeinträchtigungen konfrontiert. Der Klimawandel-Vulnerabilitätsindex (CVI) ist eine Methode zur schnellen Bewertung des Risikos des Klimawandels für Welterbestätten (Natur-, Kultur- oder gemischte Stätten). Die Methode beruht auf Experteneinschätzungen und der besten verfügbaren Klimawissenschaft.

Von 2019–2021 wurde die CVI-Methode im Weltnaturerbe Wattenmeer erprobt. Die beiden Phasen des CVI wurden in zwei eigenständigen Workshops mit führenden internationalen Wattenmeer-Expert*innen aus verschiedenen wissenschaftlichen und akademischen Bereichen durchgeführt: Phase 1 konzentrierte sich auf den außergewöhnlichen universellen Wert (OUV) des Weltnaturerbes, dieser Workshop fand in Hamburg statt (10.–11. Februar 2020); Phase 2 hatte die Gefährdung der Gemeinschaft als Thema, der Workshop wurde online abgehalten (16.–17. Februar 2021). Der vorliegende Bericht fasst die Ergebnisse der beiden Workshops zusammen.

Die drei wichtigsten Klimastressoren, die die größten Auswirkungen auf den OUV des Wattenmeeres haben, sind:

- Temperaturentwicklung (Luft und/oder Wasser),
- extreme Temperaturereignisse und
- Anstieg des Meeresspiegels.

Diese zeigten sich über die beiden betrachteten Zeiträume (bis ca. 2050 und ca. 2100) hinweg als konsistent, wobei ein Klimaszenario mit hohen Emissionen (RCP8.5) angewandt wurde, das hinsichtlich der gegenwärtigen globalen Klimapolitik am wahrscheinlichsten erscheint. **Die Vulnerabilität des OUV wurde für beide Zeiträume als hoch** (die höchste Kategorie) eingeschätzt. Während die Vulnerabilität im Hinblick auf die beiden

temperaturbedingten Klimastressoren in beiden Zeiträumen als hoch bewertet wurde, stieg die Vulnerabilität für die Auswirkungen des Meeresspiegelanstiegs von niedrig im Jahr 2050 auf hoch im Jahr 2100. Insgesamt gesehen und für beide individuellen Zeithorizonte besteht die Möglichkeit eines großen Verlusts oder einer erheblichen Veränderung der meisten Werte, die den OUV ausmachen.

Die Bewertung der Gefährdung der Gemeinschaft wurde als einheitliche Einschätzung für das gesamte Gebiet durchgeführt, was aufgrund der hohen Komplexität des Wattenmeeres und der Vielfalt der dort lebenden Gemeinschaften einige Herausforderungen mit sich brachte. Die Workshop-Teilnehmenden einigten sich auf qualitative Schlussfolgerungen, z. B. dass die Einflüsse des Klimawandels auf Wirtschaftssektoren und auf die Werte des Gebiets getrennt bewertet werden sollten. Es bestand auch Einigkeit über noch offene Fragen, einschließlich der Notwendigkeit, Forschungsfragen systematisch zu identifizieren und die Wechselwirkungen zwischen wirtschaftlichen, sozialen und kulturellen Werten und dem OUV unter dem Einfluss des Klimawandels weiter zu analysieren und zu bewerten.

Der Blick durch die Brille des Welterbes und seines OUV erwies sich als sehr hilfreich für Managementüberlegungen zum systematischen Schutz des OUV des Weltnaturerbes Wattenmeer. Die Ergebnisse des CVI-Prozesses flossen in den „SIMP Integrierenden Managementplan für das EINE Weltnaturerbe Wattenmeer“ ein, der parallel zum CVI-Prozess entwickelt wurde. Die Ergebnisse dienten auch als Grundlage für die Festlegung von Managementzielen für das Weltnaturerbe Wattenmeer in einem Entwurf für eine Ministererklärung der Trilateralen Wattenmeerzusammenarbeit für den Zeitraum 2022–2026 und als Beitrag für den dritten Zyklus der regelmäßigen Berichterstattung an die UNESCO.

Samenvatting

Nederlands

Klimaatverandering is de snelst toenemende mondiale bedreiging voor Werelderfgoederen. Op de hele wereld ondervinden Werelderfgoedlocaties al aanzienlijke negatieve gevolgen, schade en achteruitgang. De Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) is een methode om snel het risico van klimaatverandering voor Werelderfgoedlocaties (natuurlijke, culturele of een combinatie van beiden) in kaart te brengen. Dit gebeurt door middel van beoordeling door experts en op basis van de best beschikbare gegevens uit de klimaatwetenschap.

Van 2019-2021 werd de CVI-methode in een pilotproject in het Werelderfgoed Waddenzee toegepast. De twee fasen van de CVI werden in twee afzonderlijke workshops behandeld door toonaangevende internationale Waddenzee-experts die verschillende wetenschappelijke en academische sectoren vertegenwoordigden. Fase 1 draaide om de Uitzonderlijke Universele Waarde (Outstanding Universal Value, OUV) van het Werelderfgoed Waddenzee. Deze workshop werd gehouden in Hamburg, Duitsland (10-11 februari 2020). Fase 2 ging over

“Community Vulnerability”, deze workshop vond online plaats (16-17 februari 2021). Dit rapport vat de resultaten van beide workshops samen.

De drie belangrijkste klimaatstressoren waarvan bleek dat ze de grootste impact hebben op de OUV van de Waddenzee waren:

- temperatuurontwikkeling (lucht en/of water);
- extreme temperaturen; en
- zeespiegelstijging.

Deze waren consistent in de twee tijdsbestekken die in beschouwing werden genomen (rond 2050 en rond 2100), waarbij gebruik werd gemaakt van een klimaatscenario met hoge emissies (RCP8.5). Dat is het meest waarschijnlijke resultaat van het huidige wereldwijde beleid met betrekking tot de uitstoot van broeikasgassen. **De kwetsbaarheid van de OUV werd beoordeeld als Hoog** (de hoogste categorie) voor beide tijdsbestekken. Terwijl de kwetsbaarheid voor de twee temperatuurgerelateerde klimaatstressoren in beide tijdsbestekken als Hoog werd beoordeeld, escaleerde de kwetsbaarheid voor de gevolgen van zeespiegelstijging van Laag rond 2050 naar Hoog rond 2100. Over het geheel en voor beide tijdsbestekken is er een risico op een groot verlies aan of aanzienlijke verandering van het merendeel van de kernwaarden die de OUV bepalen.

De beoordeling van de ‘Community Vulnerability’ (kwetsbaarheid van de gemeenschap) is uitgevoerd als één evaluatie voor het hele gebied. Dit ging gepaard met een aantal uitdagingen omdat het Waddengebied heel complex is en er vele verschillende gemeenschappen leven. Deelnemers aan de workshop waren het eens over kwalitatieve bevindingen, bijvoorbeeld dat de gevolgen van klimaatverandering voor economische sectoren en voor de waarden van het gebied los van elkaar moeten worden beoordeeld. Eens was men het ook over open vragen, waaronder de noodzaak om stelselmatig onderzoeksvragen te identificeren en om de onderlinge relaties tussen economische, sociale en culturele waarden en de OUV onder invloed van klimaatverandering verder te analyseren en te beoordelen.

De benadering vanuit de invalshoek van het Werelderfgoed met de bijhorende OUV bleek zeer nuttig voor beheersmatige overwegingen met het doel de OUV consequent te waarborgen. De resultaten van het CVI-proces werden gebruikt voor het “SIMP Integraal Beheerplan voor ÉÉN Werelderfgoed Waddenzee”, dat parallel aan de CVI-toepassing werd ontwikkeld. Verder hielpen de bevindingen bij het vaststellen van beheerdoelen voor het Werelderfgoed in een concept Ministeriële Verklaring voor de periode 2022-2026 van de Trilaterale Waddenzee Samenwerking. Daarnaast werden ze als input voor de 3e cyclus van de periodieke UNESCO-rapportage gebruikt.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background – why the Wadden Sea?

Climate change is the fastest growing global threat to World Heritage properties (Osipova et al. 2017) many of which – natural, cultural and mixed – are already being impacted. The severity of current climate impacts on individual World Heritage (WH) properties varies, as do the range of climate drivers causing those impacts, and the rate at which they are occurring. In most cases, climate change impacts result in a degradation of the attributes¹ (see figure 2.3) that collectively convey the Outstanding Universal Value (OUV). OUV is the central concept for World Heritage properties and the basis for its inscription on the World Heritage List.

In September 2018, a presentation about a then-new methodology (the Climate Vulnerability Index, CVI) was given to key members of the Common Wadden Sea Secretariat (CWSS) and the Trilateral Task Group Climate (TG-C; now Expert Group-Climate Change Adaptation, EG-C), including the Acting Chair and Secretary of the EG-C. The CVI had been developed to assess the vulnerability of World Heritage properties to climate change.

In 2019, the Wadden Sea World Heritage property celebrated its 10th anniversary of UNESCO World Heritage inscription. As for other World Heritage properties, the Wadden Sea is vulnerable to climate change effects (see Zijlstra et al. 2020 for an overview on climate change and its influence on the Wadden Sea World Heritage, which was used for the CVI). The extent to which a variety of climate change stressors will impact the OUV of the Wadden Sea was, however, not yet clear, nor was it clear which of these stressors should be considered the most significant. The Wadden Sea World Heritage property was considered a good candidate for a workshop given:

- the fact the Wadden Sea World Heritage property is a transboundary (tri-national) property posing an additional challenge for managing climate change adaptation,
- the existing expertise on climate change within the Trilateral Wadden Sea Corporation (TWSC); and
- the need to identify priority issues for climate change adaptation and to consider a broader, globally consistent approach to assessing climate change.

There was widespread support for trialling the CVI in the Wadden Sea and to gain experience with the CVI process. As governing body of the Trilateral Wadden Sea Cooperation (TWSC), the trilateral Wadden Sea Board (WSB) adopted a proposal prepared by the EG-C and the Task Group World Heritage (TG-WH) to pilot the CVI as a tool to provide a comprehensive view on possible impacts of climate change on the values of the Wadden Sea. The CVI process can also help identify research questions with respect to climate change and adaptive

¹The attributes are the specific features that convey the Outstanding Universal Value (OUV); they may be tangible or intangible but are identified at the level at which management occurs within the property.

management for World Heritage properties. As the subject of climate change in the Wadden Sea is complex and the diverse group of stakeholders provides additional complexity, it was initially decided to limit the application of the CVI to the first phase (assessment of OUV Vulnerability).

On 10-11 February 2020 the CWSS organised an international expert workshop in which the impacts of climate change upon the OUV of the Wadden Sea World Heritage Site were discussed (CVI Phase 1). The trilateral EG-C and TG-WH supported the workshop preparation and the workshop was facilitated by the CVI lead developers. After the successful application of the first phase 1, Phase 2 of the CVI (Community Vulnerability) was conducted in an online format on two half-days, 16–17 February 2021. The results of the workshops were also used to further elaborate the CVI and the experience gained has been used to improve the methodology (see Section 4 box and Heron et al 2020b for more detail).

This document focuses on outcomes of the full application of the CVI method in the Wadden Sea World Heritage. It contains, in large parts, copies of the Phase 1 (OUV Vulnerability) workshop report (Heron et al. 2020b), which provides more detailed information on climate change and its influence on the Wadden Sea World Heritage, as well as learnings for the CVI methodology and its application at other sites.

1.2 Overview of the Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI)

The Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) is a rapid assessment tool to systematically assess climate change vulnerability of all types of World Heritage properties: - natural, cultural and mixed. The CVI framework (Fig. 1.1) builds upon the vulnerability framework described in the 4th Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC 2007).

The CVI comprises two phases:

- Phase 1: **OUV Vulnerability** - this assesses the exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity of key World Heritage attributes that convey the OUV of the property, assessing how they will be impacted by three key climate stressors (Figure 1.2) chosen to be the most relevant for that property; and
- Phase 2: **Community Vulnerability** based on the economic, social and cultural connections of the community associated with the World Heritage property, the dependency of the community upon the property, and the capacity of the community to adapt to climate change.

A detailed outline of the CVI process is presented in Day et al. (2020).

Figure 1.1. The CVI framework to undertake rapid assessment of climate change vulnerability of World Heritage properties and associated communities (Day et al. 2020).

	Climate Stressor	Synonyms and Associated Terms	Timeframe
Temperature	Temperature trend (air and/or water)	warming; hotter than average weather; increased evaporation; desiccation; sea-surface temperature; ocean warming	chronic
	Extreme temperature events	heatwaves; bleaching; hot spell; desiccation; marine heatwaves	acute
Water cycle	Precipitation trend	rainfall; rainstorms; showers; drizzle; heavy dew; hailstorms; sleet; snow	chronic
	Intense precipitation events	rainstorms; tropical cyclones; blizzard; storminess; extreme rainfall	acute
	Flooding (fluvial, pluvial)	runoff; soil absorption; intermittent waterways; flash flood	acute
	Drought (severity, duration, frequency)	aridity; dehydration; below average rainfall; prolonged water shortage; soil moisture	chronic
Wind & Storms	Mean wind trend	gale; windiness; change in wind direction	chronic
	Storm intensity and frequency	tropical cyclones; tornado; lightning strikes; blizzard	acute
Snow & Ice	Sea/lake ice change	ice extent; ice thickness; age of ice	chronic
	Snow cover or glacier change	snowpack; snow thickness; snow compaction; perennial snow; age of snowpack	chronic
Coastal	Sea level rise (trend)	flooding; subsidence; post-glacial rebound; ocean heat content; thermal expansion	chronic
	Coastal flood	coastal vulnerability; nuisance flooding	acute
	Storm surge	storm floods; storm tides; significant wave height; wave setup	acute
	Coastal erosion	currents; waves; sediment transport; accretion; deposition	chronic
Context-specific	e.g., Ocean acidification	pH; saturation state; acidity; calcification rate; ocean chemistry	chronic
	e.g., Radiation change	surface radiation; cloud fraction; long-wave radiation; short-wave radiation	chronic
	...		
	..		

Figure 1 2. Climate stressors used in the Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) methodology (after Day et al. 2020). Note that not all 14 listed climate stressors used generally across World Heritage properties (shown with coloured background) necessarily apply in the Wadden Sea; however, there may be one or more additional “context-specific” stressors that are applicable (see Section 4.2; Heron et al. 2020b).

2. The Wadden Sea World Heritage property

2.1 Location and description

The Wadden Sea is a serial tri-national World Heritage property, extending across the Danish Wadden Sea maritime conservation area; the German Wadden Sea National Parks of Hamburg, Lower Saxony and Schleswig-Holstein; and the Dutch Wadden Sea Conservation Area (Figure 2.1).

The property covers an area of nearly 11,500 km² (CWSS 2012) between the land-sea interface and the offshore area of the three countries, with a coastal distance of roughly 500 km.

Figure 2.1. Map of the Wadden Sea World Heritage property, which spans over the three countries Denmark, Germany and the Netherlands (source: CWSS).

The Wadden Sea was inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List in 2009, in recognition of the 'Outstanding Universal Value' (OUV) of the site (see Figure 1.1 for boundaries) and the progress made in protecting and managing it for future generations. The initial inscription included the Dutch and German Wadden Sea; the property was extended in 2011 (Hamburg) and in 2014 (Denmark).

The Wadden Sea is a large, temperate coastal sediment exchange system – one of the last remaining large-scale, intertidal ecosystems where natural processes continue to function largely undisturbed. These dynamic circumstances have created numerous ecological niches, colonized by species that are adapted to the extreme environmental conditions. Three marine mammal species (harbour seal, grey seal, harbour porpoise), about 150 species of fish and more than 100 bird species are complemented by numerous molluscs, plants, and micro and macro flora and fauna (CWSS 2012).

With the inscription of the Wadden Sea, the World Heritage Committee obligated the Trilateral Wadden Sea Cooperation (TWSC) to protect and manage the Wadden Sea and its OUV. Since 1978, the TWSC has provided the overall common framework for the protection of the property; its cornerstones are laid down within the Joint Declaration signed by the parties in 2010 (TWSC 2010). At consecutive Trilateral Governmental Conferences and within the Wadden Sea Plan (CWSS 2010), common principles, objectives and policies have been agreed upon. The Guiding Principle, as agreed at the 1991 Wadden Sea Conference, is “to achieve, as far as possible, a natural and sustainable ecosystem in which natural processes proceed in an undisturbed way”. Further, a comprehensive set of primarily ecological Targets were agreed upon by the cooperation. These have been set in the Wadden Sea Plan (CWSS 2010), which serves as the management plan for the property with complementary regulations, plans and programmes on the regional levels in each country.

While there are differences in how the relevant national legal protection instruments are composed within the overall framework, which naturally follows from the apparent differences in legal schemes, they are basically similar in objectives, protection regulations and enforcement. Most of the nominated property is state-owned (federal or state level) and only a very small part is privately owned. The Wadden Sea is subject to comprehensive protection, management and monitoring, in both the national perspectives and the international context (which is unprecedented in terms of its integrated and harmonized approach).

2.2 Implications of World Heritage status and key values

Each World Heritage property has a Statement of OUV, which is the principal reference for protection and management of the property and provides a baseline for monitoring and reporting. The following brief description of how the Wadden Sea fulfils three World Heritage criteria is based on the Statement of OUV for the Wadden Sea World Heritage property, adopted by the World Heritage Committee in 2009 and amended in 2014 (available from <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/1314>).

- **Criterion viii - Geological processes**

Nowhere else on the planet is there such a diverse and dynamic coastline of this scale, continually being shaped by wind and tides creating a variety of coastal and sedimentary features. The Wadden Sea is unique in that it consists entirely of a sandy-muddy tidal flat and barrier system under conditions of rising sea level, which contains examples of post-

glacial coastal geomorphology and dynamic interactions of physical and biological processes.

- **Criterion ix - Ecological and biological processes**

Nature has provided an invaluable record of past and ongoing dynamic adaptation of plants, animals and their coastal environments to global change. The productivity of biomass is the highest in the world and offers food availability widely; e.g., for fish, seals and birds.

- **Criterion x - Biodiversity**

Despite its tranquil appearance, the Wadden Sea World Heritage is among the largest wildernesses in Europe and a one of the main hotspots of biodiversity in the world. It sustains over 10,000 species of plants and animals and it is one of the main hotspots of global biodiversity. In addition, it plays an indispensable role well beyond its borders: the richness of local species is crucial for up to 12 million migratory birds that make a stopover in the area on their journey to their wintering and/or summering grounds.

To be deemed of OUV, a property must also meet the conditions of integrity² and/or authenticity and must have an adequate protection and management system:

- **Integrity**

The Wadden Sea World Heritage property includes all the facets (species, habitats, processes) that constitute a natural and dynamic Wadden Sea. The area is large enough to ensure that these exceptional aspects of one of the world's first-class ecosystems of this kind are maintained and protected.

- **Protection and management**

Protection and management of the World Heritage property are effectively secured. The Wadden Sea's supreme conservation state is the result of four decades of joint nature protection efforts of Denmark, Germany and the Netherlands, where the Wadden Sea is designated as national parks and nature reserves. Working together in the Trilateral Wadden Sea Cooperation, these countries ensure the integrated management of the area – the protection of one inseparable ecosystem that knows no borders – is a joint responsibility for the world community and for the benefits of present and future generations.

Prior to the Phase 1 CVI workshop, 10 key values of the property (Figure 2.2) were identified from the Statement of OUV by the CWSS and the trilateral Task Group World Heritage (TG-WH) in their 27th meeting (May 2019). Each key value was associated with the relevant World Heritage criterion (Annex 1). Given the broad descriptive nature of these key values, measurable attributes for each described key value were identified for the CVI application (Figure 2.3 and see Section 3.2). Together, these key values and attributes form the basis for assessments made using the CVI process.

²Integrity requires assessing if the World Heritage property is of sufficient size; if its components are sufficiently complete to demonstrate OUV; and assessing what pressures threaten the site and how they are being addressed.

In addition to the key values that convey the Statement of OUV, there are other local, regional and/or national values that are still of significance. These other Significant Property Values (SPVs; Annex 2) are also impacted by climate change. SPVs may be other natural or cultural features, scenery or some intangible values (e.g., meditative walks; sounds of lapping waves, birds calling and blowing wind/rain).

Figure 2.2. Key values derived from Statement of Outstanding Universal Value by the Common Wadden Sea Secretariat and the Task Group World Heritage (Heron et al. 2020b).

Figure 2.3. Hierarchy of World Heritage terminology as applied for the Wadden Sea (after Heron et al. 2020a).

3. Applying the Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) to the Wadden Sea World Heritage property

3.1 The CVI process

For the Wadden Sea, phase 1 of the CVI process to assess OUV Vulnerability was undertaken in February 2020 in Hamburg, Germany. Phase 2 to assess Community Vulnerability was conducted online in February 2021. Participants comprised key international Wadden Sea experts representing different scientific and academic sectors (see Annex 3 and 4 for agenda and participating institutions).

While much of the analysis was conducted during the workshops, substantial preparations were undertaken in advance by the workshop Steering Group and the participants, including understanding the breakdown of key values and attributes from the Statement of OUV and identification of Significant Property Values before Phase 1 (see Heron et al 2020b for more detail), and getting acquainted with the Phase 1 results by means of written and video information before Phase 2.

In both assessment phases, the CVI process employs both plenary sessions and breakout groups. Plenary sessions were used for presentations, discussions and to compile information from the breakout groups. For some elements of the process, breakout groups approached tasks in different (but equally effective) ways. In all cases, outcomes from the groups were brought together in plenary to resolve any differences and reach the final conclusions. Within the CVI framework (Fig. 1.1; Day et al. 2020), the OUV Vulnerability (determined in Phase 1) becomes the basis for assessing the Community Vulnerability (in Phase 2). The outcomes from Phase 1 are summarised here from their full description in Heron et al. (2020b).

3.2 Phase 1: Evaluation of current condition and trend of the key values

Assessment of the current condition and the trend in condition since inscription (2009) was undertaken during the phase 1 workshop to provide participants, and other stakeholders more broadly, with a baseline from which future climate vulnerability can be considered (Table 3.1). Initially, these were to be evaluated at the level of the identified World Heritage attributes (broken down by the workshop planning committee from the key values); however, discussions during the workshop determined that it was appropriate to assess many at the key value level. This was either because (i) the identified attributes could not be distinguished or differentiated for the purpose of assessing condition and trend; or (ii) there was no distinction between the assessed condition and trend across the attributes. As such, assessments are reported at the attribute level only when necessary.

There was agreement amongst many participants that the historical context of the Wadden Sea system is over much longer temporal scales than is reflected in the period since inscription (in 2009), which may be considered a somewhat arbitrary benchmark. For example, loss of marshland over the last 1,000 years (up to 50 km inshore from the current coastline) and blocking of fish migration in some areas occurred prior to the designation of protected areas (around the 1980s), which preceded World Heritage inscription. Therefore, many of the elements discussed were assessed as good with some concerns and stable due to this short timeframe, while consideration of a longer timeframe for the system may lead to a different assessment.

Table 3.1. Wadden Sea key values (derived from the Statement of Outstanding Universal Value by the Trilateral Task Group World Heritage) and attributes (developed by the Steering Group), together with the assessed current condition and trend since inscription in 2009. These may not reflect the condition and trend with respect to a longer timeframe; i.e., prior to inscription. Legend (on page 16) adapted from IUCN (2012). (after Heron et al. 2020b)

Key value	Attributes [cross-reference]	Current Condition and Trend
1. Unbroken tidal flat and barrier system	1a. Extent and distribution of mud flats, sand shoals, and barrier islands	
2. Geomorphological diversity	2a. Barrier islands (incl. ongoing forming or erosion of island/sand banks)	
	2b. Tidal flats, gullies, channels, ebb-tidal deltas	
	2c. Sub-tidal shoals	
	2d. Sand dunes, beaches	
3. On-going geomorphological processes	3a. Geomorphological processes (e.g., sediment movement by waves, current and wind), accretion/sedimentation patterns, erosion)	
4. Intact natural intertidal ecosystems	4a. Estuaries, tidally influenced transition zones	
	4b. Coastal wetlands (e.g., saltmarshes, beaches and dunes) [see also 8c]	
5. Linked geomorphological and biophysical processes	5a. Numbers and distribution of species typical for Wadden Sea ecosystems (e.g., species adapted to salt marshes or wet dunes, sediment gradient of tidal flats).	
	5b. Ecological processes (e.g., primary production, predation, particle feeding, recruitment, connectivity)	
	5c. Bio-geomorphological interactions (e.g., eelgrass meadows slow down flow, trap suspended particles, raising the seabed, mussel beds. Seabed reworking by infauna changes the sedimentary composition)	

Key value	Attributes [cross-reference]	Current Condition and Trend
6. High biomass production	6a. Fish stocks [see also 7c]	
	6b. Birds [see also 7a & 8d]	
	6c. Filter feeders (e.g., shellfish, mussels)	
	6d. Suspension feeders (e.g., sandworms/ lugworms - largest worm population worldwide)	
	6e. Productivity (high bacterial remineralization, strong import of organic matter, high microphytobenthos production)	
7. Migratory birds and other wildlife	7a. Migratory birds [see also 9a-9c]	
	7b. Marine mammals (e.g., common harbour seal, grey seal, harbour porpoise)	
	7c. Diadromous fish (e.g., flounder, smelt, eel)	
8. High biodiversity (flora and fauna)	8a. Subtidal fauna/flora (e.g., shrimp, fish, sponges, tunicates, harbour porpoise)	
	8b. Intertidal fauna/flora (e.g., crabs, mussels, oysters, seagrass)	
	8c. Dunal fauna/flora (e.g., saltmarsh, grassland, Kentish Plover, Little Tern, Snow Bunting)	
	8d. Important bird breeding areas (e.g., Eurasian Spoonbill, Avocet, Gull-billed Tern, Sandwich Tern) [see also 6b, 10a & 10b]	
9. Staging, moulting and wintering area for migratory birds	9a. Staging areas (e.g., important for Bar-tailed Godwit, Grey Plover) [see also 7a & 10a]	
	9b. Moulting areas (e.g., important for Common Shelduck, Common Eider and Common Scoter) [see also 7a & 10a]	
	9c. Over-wintering areas (e.g., important for Great Ringed Plover, Dunlin, Herring Gull, Redshank) [see also 7a & 10a]	
10. Key migratory stopover (low disturbance, food availability)	10a. Food availability and quality for migratory birds	

Current Condition	Criteria
Good	The site's values are in good condition and are likely to be maintained for the foreseeable future, provided that current conservation measures are maintained.
Good with some concern	While some concerns exist, with minor additional conservation measures the site's values are likely to be essentially maintained over the long-term.
Significant concern	The site's values are threatened and/or are showing signs of deterioration. Significant additional conservation measures are needed to maintain and/or restore values over the medium to long-term.
Critical	The site's values are severely threatened and/or deteriorating. Immediate large-scale additional conservation measures are needed to maintain and/or restore the site's values over the short to medium-term or the values may be lost.

Trends			
Unknown			

3.3 Phase 1: Key climate stressors

A list of 15 climate stressors likely to impact a broad range of World Heritage properties was provided to the participants as part of the CVI process (Figure 1.2). Several participants suggested that for Wadden Sea coastal erosion is an inherent process and should not be considered as a stressor. In addition, an inter-relation of climate stressors in the list was also noted, such as where one listed stressor results from the combined effects of other listed stressors (e.g., Coastal erosion may result from combined effects of Sea level rise and Storm surge). Therefore, it was decided that 'Coastal erosion' should not be selected as climate stressor but rather direct selection to the underpinning stressor/s that lead to altered erosion (e.g., Sea level rise). Further, it was decided to add Ocean acidification to the list as a 'context-specific' climate stressor.

Application of the CVI process typically occurs for a single future timeframe; however, the Wadden Sea workshop produced much discussion about the value of considering both ca. 2050 and ca. 2100, especially as climate-related tipping points are projected for the period between these times. As such, the workshop was quickly pivoted to allow for both timeframes to be assessed. In both cases, the workshop considered a high-emissions ('business-as-usual') climate scenario informed by model projections under Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) 8.5.

From the agreed upon list of climate stressors (Figure 1.2), breakout groups of participants were asked to select up to three climate stressors most likely to impact each described key value for the timeframe under consideration. Combining inputs from the breakout groups, the top three climate stressors for each key value (including equal-third) were used to then select the three key climate stressors for the property (Table 3.2; Figure 3.2).

Assessment for ca. 2050

For the ca. 2050 timeframe these were determined to be (i) Temperature trend (air and/or water); (ii) Extreme temperature events; and (iii) Sea level rise, each considered to impact upon the same number of key values. While 'Coastal erosion' had been identified by several participants as a climate stressor in the pre-workshop tasks (light blue in Figure 3.1), the decision during the workshop was to select the underpinning stressor/s that led to altered sediment dynamics, as noted previously.

Table 3.2. Climate stressors identified as likely to have the greatest impact for each of 10 key values of OUV for ca. 2050. Marked cells indicate that the climate stressor was in the top three responses (including equal-third) for each key value. (after Heron et al. 2020b)

Key values of OUV	Temperature trend (air and/or water)	Extreme temperature events	Precipitation trend	Intense precipitation events	Flooding (fluvial, pluvial)	Drought (severity, duration, frequency)	Mean wind trend	Storm intensity and frequency	Sea/lake ice change	Snow cover change	Sea level rise (trend)	Coastal flood	Storm surge	Coastal erosion	Ocean acidification
Unbroken tidal flat and barrier system								X			X		X		
Geomorphological diversity								X			X		X		
On-going dynamic geomorphological processes						X		X			X				
Intact natural intertidal ecosystems	X	X									X				
Linked geomorphological and biophysical processes	X	X						X							
High productivity (fish, shellfish, birds)	X	X	X			X									
Migratory birds and other wildlife	X	X						X			X		X		
High biodiversity (flora, fauna)	X	X				X									
Staging, moulting and wintering area for migratory birds	X	X									X				
Key migratory stopover (low disturbance, food availability)	X	X									X				
Total	7	7	1	0	0	3	0	5	0	0	7	0	3	0	0

Figure 3.1. Histogram of impacts on 10 key values of OUV from 15 climate stressors whose impacts were assessed for ca. 2050. Pre-workshop responses without specifying a time-period are shown in light blue. Note that ‘Coastal erosion’ was not considered during the workshop. (after Heron et al. 2020b)

Assessment for ca. 2100

For the ca. 2100 timeframe the same stressors as for 2050 were determined, but with Sea level rise considered to impact upon the greatest number, and in fact all, of the key values (Table 3.3; Figure 3.2). While Ocean acidification was identified during the breakout groups as having potential impact on several key values, the specifics of and level of certainty regarding those impacts were insufficient at the time to include this as a key climate stressor.

Table 3.3. Climate stressors identified as likely to have the greatest impact for each of 10 key values of OUV for ca. 2100. Marked cells indicate that the climate stressor was in the top three responses for that key value. Ocean acidification was noted by participants as of potential importance but requiring further research to overcome uncertainty in the level of impact. (after Heron et al. 2020b)

Key values of OUV	Climate stressors														
	Temperature trend (air and/or water)	Extreme temperature events	Precipitation trend	Intense precipitation events	Flooding (fluvial, pluvial)	Drought (severity, duration, frequency)	Mean wind trend	Storm intensity and frequency	Sea/lake ice change	Snow cover change	Sea level rise (trend)	Coastal flood	Storm surge	Coastal erosion	Ocean acidification
Unbroken tidal flat and barrier system								X			X		X		?
Geomorphological diversity								X			X		X		?
On-going dynamic geomorphological processes						X		X			X				?
Intact natural intertidal ecosystems	X	X						X			X				
Linked geomorphological and biophysical processes	X	X						X			X				
High productivity (fish, shellfish, birds)	X	X									X				?
Migratory birds and other wildlife	X	X									X				
High biodiversity (flora, fauna)	X	X				X					X				?
Staging, moulting and wintering area for migratory birds	X	X									X				?
Key migratory stopover (low disturbance, food availability)	X	X									X		X		
Total	7	7	0	0	0	2	0	5	0	0	10	0	3	0	76

Figure 3.2. Histogram of impacts on 10 key values of OUV from 15 climate stressors whose impacts were assessed for ca. 2100. The hatched column indicates that Ocean acidification was noted by participants as of potential importance but requiring further research to overcome uncertainty in the level of impact. Pre-workshop responses without specifying a time-period are shown in the lighter blue. Note that ‘Coastal erosion’ was not considered during the workshop. (after Heron et al. 2020b)

3.4 Phase 1: OUV Vulnerability

Assessment for ca. 2050

Exposure to climate stressors and the sensitivity of the OUV system to these are used within the CVI process to assess the potential impacts of each key climate stressor. At this point in the CVI process, consideration is given to all key values collectively, rather than individually. The level of **exposure** (i.e., the nature, magnitude and rate of climatic and associated changes) of the OUV system to each of the three key climate stressors was assessed using a five-point categorical scale (Day et al. 2020). Modifiers assessing temporal scale and trend were also evaluated, potentially amplifying the level of exposure. The measure of the **sensitivity** (i.e., the degree to which the OUV is affected, either adversely or beneficially, by climate variability or change) of the OUV system to each of the three key climate stressors was also assessed using a five-point categorical scale, with modifiers similarly applied to incorporate spatial scale and compounding factors (Day et al. 2020). Compounding factors are non-climate factors that lead to increased impacts upon a property when operating together with climate stressors. For the Wadden Sea, these may include cumulative impacts on the site due to increasing tourism. It was noted during the Phase 1 workshop that while there may not be manageable solutions to reduce effects from climate change, there exists capacity to reduce impacts of compounding stressors.

Combining inputs from the breakout groups, the likelihood of exposure of Wadden Sea to Temperature trend and Sea level rise were assessed as Very likely (>90%). While initially assessed as Likely (67-90%), consideration of modifiers raised the assessment of exposure to Extreme temperature events also to the Very likely category. Evaluation of sensitivity of the OUV system to Temperature trend and Extreme temperature events was initially at the

Moderate level for both, with the former assessment elevated to the High level after considering modifiers. Similarly, the sensitivity to Sea level rise was raised to Moderate from the initial assessment of Low. Definitions of each sensitivity level are provided in Day et al. (2020). As a result, the **potential impact** was determined to be Extreme with respect to Temperature trend (the highest category of the four-point scale) and High for each of Extreme temperature events and Sea level rise (Table 3.2).

Table 3.4. Rapid assessment of OUV Vulnerability to identified three key climate stressors for the 2050s. Assessed values of exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity contribute to derived outcomes of potential impact and OUV Vulnerability. Colours refer to the elements of the CVI framework (Fig. 1.1). (after Heron et al. 2020b)

Key Climate Stressors:	Temperature trend (air and/or water)	Extreme temperature events	Sea level rise (trend)
Exposure	Very likely	Likely	Very likely
Temporal scale	On-going	Frequent	On-going
Trend	Rapid increase	Moderate/Rapid increase	Slow/Moderate increase
Exposure	Very likely ○○○●	Very likely ○○○●	Very likely ○○○●
Sensitivity	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Spatial scale	Widespread	Extensive	Extensive
Compounding factors	Medium/High probability	Medium probability	Medium probability
Sensitivity	High ○○○○	Moderate ○○●○○	Moderate ○○●○○
Potential impact	Extreme ○○○●	High ○○○○	High ○○○○
Local management response	Low	Low	High
Scientific/technical support	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate/High
Effectiveness	Low	Very low/Low	Moderate/High
Adaptive capacity	Low ○●○○	Very low ●○○○	High ○○○●
OUV Vulnerability	High ○○●	High ○○●	Low ●○○
Combined OUV Vulnerability	High ○○●		

Adaptive capacity describes the potential or capability to adjust to climate change, to moderate potential damage, to take advantage of opportunities, or respond to the consequences. In the CVI framework, adaptive capacity of a World Heritage property is considered in terms of:

- a. the local management response,
- b. the level of scientific and/or technical support, and
- c. the effectiveness of these to address the climate stressor being considered.

Each of these components are assessed on a four-point scale, with the **adaptive capacity** also determined on a four-point scale (Day et al. 2020). As for exposure and sensitivity, inputs from breakout groups were combined during in plenary sessions. Together with the assessment of potential impact, the adaptive capacity is used to determine the vulnerability of OUV for each key climate stressor, which are combined to give the OUV Vulnerability for the property.

Local management and the level of support were assessed as Low and Moderate for the stressors Temperature trend and Extreme temperature events, respectively. The measure of effectiveness of actions was evaluated as lower for Extreme temperature events (Low/Very low) than for Temperature trend (Low), which led to a distinction in the overall adaptive capacity (Very low with respect to Extreme temperature events, Low for Temperature trend). In contrast, for Sea level rise, local management within the ca. 2050 timeframe was assessed as High, and the scientific/technical support and effectiveness were both Moderate/High, resulting in an overall evaluation of adaptive capacity of High. As a result, the vulnerability of OUV (on a three-point scale, low to high) was determined to be High for Extreme temperature events and Temperature trend, and Low with respect to Sea level rise. Combining these, the **OUV Vulnerability** for Wadden Sea was determined as High for the ca. 2050 timeframe (Table 3.2).

This ca. 2050 assessment of OUV Vulnerability was compared with previous applications of the CVI process using similar timeframes – the natural property Shark Bay, Western Australia (Heron et al. 2020a) and the cultural property Heart of Neolithic Orkney (Scotland; Day et al. 2019). In all cases the OUV Vulnerability was in the highest category; however, examining the assessed vulnerability of OUV at the level of the three key climate stressors shows variation between the applications. For Shark Bay, vulnerability was determined as High for all three key climate stressors; for Heart of Neolithic Orkney, two stressors led to High vulnerability with the third evaluated as Moderate. It is important to note that this description is not intended to imply a ranking but rather to indicate that there is a spectrum of outcomes when using the CVI methodology. Most importantly for Wadden Sea is the rapid assessment outcome of High OUV Vulnerability.

Assessment for ca. 2100

For ca. 2100, the likelihood of exposure of Wadden Sea was assessed as Very likely (>90%) for all three key climate stressors. Sensitivity of the OUV system was initially at the High level for all stressors and was elevated to High/Very high for Temperature trend and Sea level rise after considering modifiers. The potential impact was determined to be Extreme for all three key climate stressors (Table 3.5).

While assessments for exposure and sensitivity were elevated, those for components of adaptive capacity were typically reduced from the ca. 2050 analysis. This resulted in evaluations of adaptive capacity as Very low for Temperature trend and Extreme temperature events, and Low for Sea level rise. As a result, the vulnerability of OUV was determined to be High for all three key climate stressors, with the OUV Vulnerability for Wadden Sea for the ca. 2100 timeframe determined as High (Table 3.5).

While the key climate stressors identified act on different timeframes (and therefore had different contributions to the two assessments), the sensitivity and adaptive capacity of the OUV system may not change. The workshop analysis showed that, ultimately, there was minimal difference in the overall assessment of OUV Vulnerability.

Table 3.5. Rapid assessment of OUV Vulnerability for ca. 2100 (see caption of Table 3.4 for additional detail). (after Heron et al. 2020b)

Key Climate Stressors:	Temperature trend (air and/or water)	Extreme temperature events	Sea level rise (trend)
Exposure	Very likely	Very likely	Very likely
Temporal scale	On-going	Frequent	On-going
Trend	Rapid increase	Rapid increase	Moderate/Rapid increase
Exposure	Very likely ○○○●	Very likely ○○○●	Very likely ○○○●
Sensitivity	High	High	High
Spatial scale	Widespread	Extensive/Widespread	Extensive/Widespread
Compounding factors	Medium/High probability	Medium probability	High probability
Sensitivity	High/Very high ○○○●	High ○○○●	High/Very high ○○○●
Potential impact	Extreme ○○○●	Extreme ○○○●	Extreme ○○○●
Local management response	Low	Low	Low/Moderate
Scientific/technical support	Low/Moderate	Low/Moderate	Moderate/High
Effectiveness	Very low-negligible	Very low-negligible	Low
Adaptive capacity	Very low ●○○○	Very low ●○○○	Low ○●○○
OUV Vulnerability	High ○○●	High ○○●	High ○○●
Combined OUV Vulnerability	High ○○●		

3.5 Phase 2: Community Vulnerability

Community Vulnerability is evaluated in the CVI process by considering economic, social, and cultural (ESC) aspects of the community associated with the property. Economic aspects are considered as high-level business types associated with the property. Social and cultural connections consider intangible links of the community with the property (e.g., societal cohesion, attachment to place; see Day et al 2020) and are evaluated for three people groups: locals, other nationals (or regional peoples) and internationals. The key difference between these analyses is that social connections are about activity associated with the property and so require a physical interaction, whereas cultural connections are about individual and communal identity for which a physical interaction is not necessary.

The Wadden Sea is highly complex and was, at the time, considered to be the most complex World Heritage property assessed using the CVI; e.g., due to multiple jurisdictions with some differences in management approaches and with cultural differences and nuances.

The CVI assessment of the Community Vulnerability builds upon the Phase 1 assessment of OUV Vulnerability (i.e., the level of vulnerability of the key values that collectively comprise the OUV). It is the implications of the OUV Vulnerability for the surrounding community that depends upon the World Heritage property that is assessed in Phase 2. Whilst these two phases can be undertaken in a single assessment, for the Wadden Sea they were undertaken separately (February 2020 and February 2021, respectively). In addition, it had been pre-determined that the Community Vulnerability assessment would be undertaken with a whole-of-property perspective (i.e., ONE Wadden Sea).

Economic activities

In preparation for the workshop, the workshop organisation committee identified six economic sectors for inclusion in the analysis. These included the five key topics that were selected for [The SIMP Integrated Management Plan for ONE Wadden Sea World Heritage](#), which was under development at the time of the workshop (CWSS 2023a), plus Agriculture. Information on the first five sectors is also compiled in the respective thematic Quality Status Reports (QSR) of the Wadden Sea, referenced below.

- Energy/infrastructure (Baer & Nehls 2017; CWSS 2023a) is well regulated within the property; however, sectoral activities in adjacent land and sea areas may disturb migratory routes and breeding areas (e.g., of birds, marine mammals). Supporting infrastructure (e.g., transmission cables, power stations, bridges) and other related factors may have additional effects upon the natural values.
- Shipping/harbours (Bahlke 2017; CWSS 2023a) in and near the Wadden Sea are internationally significant, comprising some of Northern Europe's largest ports and some of the busiest shipping routes in the world. Maintenance needs and disturbance events (accidents, noise) present potential threats to the environment.

- Fisheries (Baer et al. 2017; CWSS 2023a), including aquaculture, can have wider impacts on the marine ecological system. Two key species are the North Sea brown shrimp (*Crangon crangon*) and the blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*).
- Tourism (Bjarnason et al. 2017; CWSS 2023a) is an important sector, especially for the island communities, requiring effective management to avoid negative impacts and promote conservation. Tourism includes nature experiences; health and well-being activities; and provision of services (transportation, accommodation).
- Coastal protection (Zijlstra et al. 2017; CWSS 2023a) of communities and assets from flooding and erosion has long been a requirement of the region. The use of dykes, groins and sand nourishment has evolved, including more recent use of nature-based measures. Continued vigilance is necessary as the challenges of a naturally dynamic coast and its interconnectivity with the hinterland are amplified by sea level rise.
- Agriculture has been important to the region for over a century, with technological developments during that time (e.g., machinery, use of fertilisers and pesticides) providing economic benefits but also linked to increased pressures upon the broader system (e.g., disease, algal blooms).

Prior to the workshop, participants were asked to rank the six pre-defined economic sectors in order of their dependence upon the World Heritage values and attributes. The responses received indicated that Tourism, Fisheries and Coastal Protection had the highest dependence upon World Heritage. During the workshop, this view was confirmed (Figure 3.3). Consideration of additional sectors, such as the Health sector, was suggested by participants for the future.

Participants were asked to assess how the loss of World Heritage values would affect each economic sector in the future (“dependency”) and the existing capacity to adapt to that (“adaptive capacity”). While economic dependency and adaptive capacity of all economic sectors were discussed in breakout groups during the workshop, the synthesis in plenary focused on the three deemed to have the greatest dependence upon the World Heritage values (Tourism, Fishery and Coastal Protection).

Breakout groups conveyed their decisions for the economic dependency and adaptive capacity related to all sectors (Table 3.6). However, participants also reported difficulties to determine the extent to which loss of World Heritage values due to the key climate stressors would change the direct economic value of the sectors in future. For example, would tourism decline if the area of tidal flats reduces or migratory birds became less abundant; or would tourism adapt to new forms linked to other World Heritage attributes (e.g., beach tourism). Some breakout groups considered of the direct effect of climate stressors on the sectors (rather than through the lens of the OUV) in making their assessments. As such, a direct synthesis of group discussions of the adaptive capacity of sectors on changes in the OUV was not possible. Importantly, workshop participants considered that direct impacts of climate change on the economy were potentially greater than those only looking through the lens of loss of World Heritage values.

Figure 3.3. Ranking of the relative dependence of economic sectors upon the World Heritage values conducted during the workshop. The three highest ranked sectors were consistent with a pre-workshop analysis.

Table 3.6. Synthesis of comments from breakout groups and participant feedback related to economic dependency and adaptive capacity. Those associated with a loss of key values (of OUV) are shown in bold.

Sector	Summary of comments on Economic Dependency	Summary of comments on Economic Adaptive Capacity
Energy/ Infrastructure	Independent of OUV, not much change by 2050.	Loss of OUV irrelevant or causing minimal impact.
Shipping/ Harbours	Harbours affected by sea-level rise; Local shipping (ferries) affected by changes to Tourism.	Loss of OUV irrelevant or causing minimal impact; The need for Harbours to adapt is small by 2050 (but larger beyond); Shipping has high adaptive capacity to sea-level rise.
Agriculture	Impacts of drought (salinisation) and sea-level rise not related to OUV; Drainage may have links to loss of OUV; however, these are complex.	Limited capacity to adapt to increased salinity in the hinterland.
Coastal Protection	Minimal effect by 2050 , but will be greater with accelerating sea-level rise.	Dikes are the current strategy but require time to implement /modify; nature-based approaches are being considered. Adaptive capacity is expected to be lower post-2050, so action now is important
Fishery	OUV biodiversity loss ; Needed dedicated experts (fishers).	limited potential adaptations (regulatory system is static and does not allow different types of catch); Innovation varies geographically.
Tourism	Difficult to assess, as there is also a positive effect of nicer climate conditions; World Heritage will remain important (e.g., scenery) even with OUV loss; OUV biodiversity loss has effect.	Sector is partly independent, well resourced.

Social and cultural connections

As noted, social and cultural connections refer to intangible links of the community with the property. Social connections are generated through physical interactions, such as contact with the natural environment (e.g., for work or rest); the use of built assets (e.g., transport infrastructure); and fostering personal satisfaction (e.g., lifestyle) or societal association (e.g., cooperative actions; Costanza et al. 2007). Workshop participants identified a variety of social connections with the Wadden Sea, including holidays & recreation; work activities; and interaction with nature (Figure 3.4-upper panel).

In contrast, cultural connections are about individual and communal identity. This may come through physical interaction; however, such affinity could also come through family history or heritage in the region (e.g., Frisian heritage) or through a similarity of attributes with other known places or experiences (e.g., intertidal wetlands, flyways). These connections may be expressed through personal qualities (such as health and identity), pleasure derived from the place (including cultural and spiritual aspects) or appreciation of environmental attributes (biodiversity, scientific heritage; Marshall et al. 2019). Workshop participants identified a variety of cultural connections with the Wadden Sea, including views to the horizon; traditions and stories; and Frisian culture (Figure 3.4-lower panel).

As for the economic connections, participants were asked to assess how the loss of World Heritage values would affect social and cultural connections in the future (“dependency”) and the existing capacity of those to adapt (“adaptive capacity”). This was undertaken for each of three people groups: locals, other nationals and internationals. Social and cultural assessments were considered “difficult to assess [due to the] difference between people outside the area and the OUV (key values) in the area”. Participants felt that they had limited expertise in these areas, indicated they were “biased by personal experience” that may not be representative of the broad population, and reported uncertainty in these assessments.

Diverse participant perspectives were both expected and considered a valuable asset of the process; however, undertaking to resolve this diversity across the entirety of the vast World Heritage property proved challenging. Given the above complexities and the need to bring the widely differing perspectives of participants together to arrive at a common assessment outcome, the time set aside for the totality of the workshop proved to be insufficient.

There was a perspective shared that while a low level of cultural connection was indicated by the workshop participants, that this was seemingly not aligned with the national (and international) recognition of the Wadden Sea as, regionally, one of the most appreciated nature areas. The understanding of its intrinsic value and a perceived desire to care for and protect the Wadden Sea would suggest a strong cultural connection and therefore higher vulnerability.

Social connections:

Cultural connections:

Figure 3.4. Word cloud of social (upper panel) and cultural (lower panel) connections with the Wadden Sea expressed by workshop participants during the second workshop. Similar responses have been clustered for presentation.

Combining the ESC assessments

The Community Vulnerability (Phase 2) workshop revealed challenges in assessing ESC dependencies to the World Heritage OUV. Furthermore, the subsequent evaluation of the ESC adaptive capacity with respect to possible changes in World Heritage key values under the selected climate change scenario proved very difficult for the participants. Several participants remarked that for most sectors (e.g., fisheries, agriculture) the direct impact of climate change on economy and community was probably higher than through the loss of World Heritage key values themselves (the latter being the workshop task).

Also, it was noted that it is very difficult to estimate the extent of potential changes as it is even more difficult to quantify the impact of climate change without any solid knowledge base. This was especially so for social and cultural factors, for which many participants expressed feeling uncomfortable and not competent enough to evaluate the existing situation or to predict future developments with sufficient certainty. For instance, how will people feel about their cultural connection to the Wadden Sea if the area were to lose its intertidal flats? As this will happen over many decades people may at the same time develop new cultural relations to the changed area.

During the workshop, participants could therefore not agree on one quantitative outcome for Community Vulnerability (e.g., a "high", "moderate" or "low" overall ESC vulnerability). Nevertheless, participants could agree on several more qualitative conclusions and identified open questions (see Section 4.1), as well as the need to systematically identify research questions. Further, there was a recognition and broad agreement that the components of the Community Vulnerability (i.e., the ESC components) were important and need to be assessed.

While participants recognised the value of including ESC analyses, several aspects seemed to be almost decoupled from World Heritage key values. The latter also represents a knowledge gap to be addressed in future, in order to further map the overall consequences of climate change for the area. Participants also indicated that assessing ESC dependencies on the OUV and climate change may not be done in one workshop, as time is far too limited and expertise from other socio-economic and sociological fields would have to be included.

Whilst the CVI process was completed based on the participant contributions, the quantitative outcome of the whole-of-property analysis is not included here based on the participants' concerns stated during and after the Phase 2 workshop.

3.6 Summary of outcomes of the CVI

The Wadden Sea World Heritage property was assessed to have the highest level of OUV Vulnerability (High) for the ca. 2050 and 2100 timeframes with respect to the three key climate stressors identified by the workshop participants: Temperature trend, Extreme temperature events and Sea level rise. Under RCP 8.5, there is the potential for major loss or substantial alteration of the majority of the attributes that convey the OUV of the World

Heritage property by 2050 (Figure 3.6). This potential loss is amplified when considering a timeframe to ca. 2100. The second phase of the CVI provided qualitative conclusions, including the need to systematically identify research questions and to further analyse and assess the interrelations between economic, social and cultural values and the OUV under climate change influence. An additional outcome of the CVI was a list of other Significant Property Values (i.e., those not included within OUV; Annex 2).

Figure 3.6. Summary of outcomes of the Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) as assessed for the Wadden Sea World Heritage property during two workshops in 2020 and 2021.

4. Conclusions and next steps

4.1 Gaps and opportunities

The considerable research conducted in the Wadden Sea has produced a wealth of knowledge; however, the following knowledge gaps were identified through the two workshops:

PHASE 1

- research towards climate change adaptation and if and how projects can involve the land behind the dyke and/or previously reclaimed land;
- a need to quantify carbon sequestration in the Wadden Sea, noting:
 - understanding carbon sequestration in salt marshes is important; and
 - existing research indicates that the water column has sufficient buffering capacities for the next hundreds of years;
- further knowledge development regarding impacts from ocean acidification (highlighted in the assessment for ca. 2100), noting that some buffering may occur due to the high amount of organic material in the Wadden Sea;
- required analysis of water temperature trend and the frequency of marine heatwaves in the Wadden Sea;
- understanding of historical and projected future alteration of the ocean current system;
- additional data needs on sediment state and balance;
- regarding specific species and habitats (possibly some identified as SPVs), prioritisation of important species for closer consideration;
- understanding of the options for adaptation measures in response to the identified key climate stressors, while maintaining the natural dynamics of the system;
- an overview of “no regret” measures (i.e., measures worth implementing regardless of the outcome particularly when consequences are uncertain) that already exist for the Wadden Sea; and
- comparative analysis of systems similar to the Wadden Sea under different climate scenarios and/or present-day climate analogues for Wadden Sea (i.e., locations whose current climate conditions are representative of projected conditions for the Wadden Sea).

PHASE 2

Research needs

- consider the application of the Ecosystem Services Approach to analyse climate change effects on the economic, social and cultural components (e.g., similar to Clarke et al. 2021). The Life Cycle Analysis is another, complementary option, both of which would require a multi-disciplinary approach.

- consider the growing evidence of the impacts of oceans and seas on human health and wellbeing (e.g., similar to Fleming et al. 2014).
- research on impacts of changes of nature values (for different reasons) on "cultural connection".
- how do cultural perceptions (several aspects) change over time and over generations?
- Wadden Sea-wide economic indicators (value, employment) were not consistently available across the span of the property.
- how will future climate change affect economic sectors; e.g., sea-level rise impacts on energy production (windmills)?
- investigate the potential discrepancy between economic de-coupling and perceived strong cultural connection with the property.

Policy and guidance gaps

- need to also include traditions, language, customs, music/ arts/crafts, religion, community values, and sense of place when considering management options for the future.
- how to include direct effects of climate change on the community aspects (ESC) that occur independent of loss of World Heritage values due to climate impacts.
- how to communicate the climate change scenarios with examples that are easy to relate to (e.g., show how loss of diversity may affect fisheries).

4.2 Management implications

The Wadden Sea is a highly dynamic and adaptive system. Yet, as also revealed during the Phase 1 workshop, there are limits to the adaptive capacity of the system to adjust to either sea level rise or temperature effects without disturbing the natural dynamics. As such, the most effective way to safeguard the OUV of the Wadden Sea is through global actions to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (and atmospheric concentration) and therefore prevent extreme climate changes. Recognising the critical need for global actions to address the primary cause of climate change (greenhouse gas emissions), management activities will have to be strategic and intentional to support the property and its values through the coming decades of increased frequency and severity of climate-related disturbance.

It was recognised that further research would be beneficial to better inform the process. However, it is important to note that management is necessary now and decisions should not await perfect information, especially given the dynamic nature of both the Wadden Sea system and climate change.

Among the three identified key climate stressors in Phase 1 of the CVI process, the temperature-related stressors (Temperature trend, Extreme temperature events) may have limited options for feasible management responses. Assisted evolution to acquire thermal

tolerance may be achievable for some sessile and motile organisms, although the cost of this approach may limit the scale of application.

In contrast, the history of management activity with respect to sea level illustrates the high level of scientific and technical capacity to support adaptation (Phase 1) of the Wadden Sea to Sea level rise. However, it is also important to note that the workshop determined the high level of adaptive capacity in 2050 would reduce to a low level by 2100 with the projected acceleration of Sea level rise towards the end of this century.

Workshop participants (Phase 1) recognised the importance of minimising other (localised) stressors on the ecosystem, particularly during periods of acute disturbance. This could involve temporary closures of some sections of the property that are being impacted (for example, by a marine heatwave) to support resistance to and recovery from climate exposure. Should such a closure be considered a viable approach, consultation with communities and industries potentially affected would be vital to the success of the intervention.

The CVI application revealed the need to systematically identify research questions and to further analyse and assess the interrelations between economic, social and cultural values and the OUV under climate change influence. For example, how dependent is tourism on the World Heritage status and the underlying quality status of natural key values that form the basis for the World Heritage status? Should the Wadden Sea change due to climate change and the World Heritage values decline, how might tourism be impacted? It should also be recognised that different communities across the vast area of the Wadden Sea may have very different perspectives on these community connections and experience different societal effects from climate change-induced impacts on the World Heritage values.

4.3 Next steps

For the Wadden Sea World Heritage site, the view through the lens of the World Heritage OUV was a very valuable exercise. The outcomes of the CVI process were seen as a rapid assessment to highlight priorities and a step along the path of action in response to climate change in the Wadden Sea. This may be followed by a comprehensive assessment of most relevant aspects of climate change in the Wadden Sea.

The CVI outcome should help to manage the World Heritage property, reporting to UNESCO on the status of the area and provide guidance on prioritising research questions. For the Wadden Sea World Heritage property, this was certainly the case for Phase 1. At the time of the workshops, the SIMP was being developed (CWSS 2023a). The outcomes of the CVI process fed into the SIMP development, in particular the identification of the 10 key values of the property (Figure 2.2) was used throughout the development phases of the SIMP, and CVI outcomes fed into chapters on climate change and adaptation.

Also results of the CVI process were considered when drafting climate change adaptation activities for the Wilhelmshaven Declaration – Ministerial Council Declaration of the 14th

Trilateral Governmental Conference on the Protection of the Wadden Sea (CWSS 2023b). Further, outcomes were used as input for the 3rd cycle UNESCO periodic reporting in 2023.

The 10 key values will be used in future work of the TWSC, in particular for the implementation of the SIMP. Further, the “view through the lens of the OUV” will be fostered in future, to ensure safeguarding the OUV of the Wadden Sea World Heritage.

Next steps may include:

- Develop and visualize simulations of the potential changes to the key values under different climate change prediction scenarios;
- Discuss ways to support the resilience of the Wadden Sea system and the people and local economies that depend on them, and define the area and topics that have to be considered for this purpose;
- Systematically identify research questions and to further analyse and assess the interrelations between economic, social and cultural values and the OUV under climate change influence

Overall, the rapid and repeatable nature of the CVI process is a strength that allows managers to re-visit these findings as part of an adaptive management strategy. Further application of the CVI will be discussed for the Wadden Sea World Heritage.

Lessons learned for future CVI applications

There were several opportunities for gaining experience in applying the CVI – and improvements for future applications. Conducting the two phases of the process in separate workshops has been demonstrated as viable (Heron et al. 2023); however, for the Wadden Sea application this separation was disadvantaged by the extended time between the two workshops (one year). This gap required that the Phase 2 participants revisit and understand the outcomes from Phase 1, as they provided a key foundation for the Phase 2 assessments. However, a significant change in the make-up of participants led to a significant loss of knowledge. The need to review Phase 1 outcomes (including decisions that led to those) during the Phase 2 workshop consumed time that could have otherwise been used for Phase 2 discussions within the time allocated. The reduced time was especially pertinent given the diversity of communities associated with the property.

A key lesson for future CVI applications from the Wadden Sea Phase 2 workshop was to trial alternative approaches to assessing Community Vulnerability in complex properties. One option, which had been recommended after the Phase 1 workshop (Heron et al. 2020b), was to undertake ESC analyses for sub-regions and then synthesise these to the whole-of-property level. This approach was used in a subsequent CVI application for the High Coast/Kvarken Archipelago (Heron et al. 2022), in which breakout groups for the Community Vulnerability assessment were re-arranged (from those of the OUV Vulnerability assessment) to contain only participants of one constituent country (Sweden and Finland). Not only did this enable focus on the distinct communities, it also provided benefit to the discussions as they could each be conducted in local language. This approach proved successful and was supported by the site managers and participants.

Scott Heron & Jon Day (CVI Developers)

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Annex 1: Key values derived from the Statement of Outstanding Universal Value

Key values identified by the Common Wadden Sea Secretariat and the trilateral Task Group World Heritage in their 27th meeting (May 2019).

Statement of OUV	Key value
Criterion (viii) – to be outstanding examples representing major stages of earth's history, including the record of life, significant on-going geological processes in the development of landforms, or significant geomorphic or physiographic features;	
The Wadden Sea is a depositional coastline of unparalleled scale and diversity. It is distinctive in being almost entirely a tidal flat and barrier system with only minor river influences and an outstanding example of the large-scale development of an intricate and complex temperate-climate sandy barrier coast under conditions of rising sea-level.	1. Scale of the extent of unbroken tidal flat and barrier system with minor river influences.
	2. Typical diversity of geomorphological features
Highly dynamic natural processes are uninterrupted across the vast majority of the property, creating a variety of different barrier islands, channels, flats, gullies, saltmarshes and other coastal and sedimentary features.	3. Dynamic on-going natural geomorphological processes, creating typical variety and spatial patterns of natural landforms
Criterion (ix) – to be outstanding examples representing significant ongoing ecological and biological processes in the evolution and development of terrestrial, fresh water, coastal and marine ecosystems and communities of plants and animals;	
The Wadden Sea includes some of the last remaining natural large-scale intertidal ecosystems, where natural processes continue to function largely undisturbed.	4. Naturalness and intactness of intertidal ecosystems
Its geological and geomorphologic features are closely entwined with biophysical processes and provide an invaluable record of the ongoing dynamic adaptation of coastal environments to global change. There are a multitude of transitional zones between land, sea and freshwater that are the basis for the species richness of the property.	5. Dynamic adaptation to linked geological, geomorphologic features with biophysical processes
The productivity of biomass in the Wadden Sea is one of the highest in the world, most significantly demonstrated in the numbers of fish, shellfish and birds supported by the property.	6. High biomass production typical for the Wadden Sea
The property is a key site for migratory birds and its ecosystems sustain wildlife populations well beyond its borders.	7. Key site for migratory birds and other wildlife populations beyond its borders.

Statement of OUV	Key value
<p>Criterion (x) – to contain the most important and significant natural habitats for in-situ conservation of biological diversity, including those containing threatened species of outstanding universal value from the point of view of science or conservation.</p>	
<p>Coastal wetlands are not always the richest sites in relation to faunal diversity, however this is not the case for the Wadden Sea. The salt marshes host around 2,300 species of flora and fauna, and the marine and brackish areas a further 2,700 species, and 30 species of breeding birds.</p>	<p>8. High biodiversity of flora and fauna typical for a natural Wadden Sea.</p>
<p>The clearest indicator of the importance of the property is the support it provides to migratory birds as a staging, moulting and wintering area. Up to 6.1 million birds can be present at the same time, and an average of 10-12 million each year pass through the property.</p>	<p>9. Staging, moulting and wintering area for migratory birds.</p>
<p>The availability of food and a low level of disturbance are essential factors that contribute to the key role of the nominated property in supporting the survival of migratory species. The property is the essential stopover that enables the functioning of the East Atlantic and African-Eurasian migratory flyways. Biodiversity on a worldwide scale is reliant on the Wadden Sea.</p>	<p>10. Essential site for functioning of the East-Atlantic Flyway</p>

Annex 2: List of other Significant Property Values (SPVs) for the Wadden Sea World Heritage property

In preparation for the CVI workshop (Phase 1), participants were asked to list other Significant Property Values (SPVs) that are not included within the OUV of the Wadden Sea property but are locally, regionally or nationally significant. Suggested values were clustered by the workshop committee and comprise natural and cultural values, human use and intangible values, with an indication of whether they occur “in”- or “out”-side the property boundary. Of note, these can be outside the property but must be linked to the property.

Summary of other Significant Property Values (SPVs) as provided by CVI workshop participants.

Broad groupings	Significant Property Values	In	Out
Archaeological heritage	Archaeological sites such as shipwrecks, dwelling mounds, pre-historic settlements and farmland (also inundated), and other sites.	x	x
Cultural heritage	Villages and historical places, historical buildings, burial places, archive of historic events, Halligen islands,		x
Nature values	Flora and fauna (including hinterland)	*	x
Land use/Landscape development	History of marsh development and human settlements, land reclamation, drainage system (ditch, waterway, sluice, pumping stations, dike), use of summerpolder, water management	x	x
Coastal engineering, historical and actual	Safety against sea: History of flood defences (actual and archaeological), such as dykes, dwelling mounds, wells.	x	x
Economy	Tourism and recreational facility, fishing/aquaculture, shipping, gas extraction,	x	x
Identity	Coastal protection measures, fisheries, living at interface land-sea, stories of the Wadden Sea, historical sites of inundated farmland and settlements, traditional practices and knowledge	x	x
Intangible values	Darkness, silence, exposure to elements, open seascape, attraction to interfaces (land water) and infinity, aesthetics, scenery	x	x
Climate mitigation	Carbon sequestration areas (Salt Marshes, Dunes, Sea Grass) CO2 mitigation - blue carbon storage.	x	x
Science	Important for understanding boundaries of sustainability. Brings "untouchable" sea floor within reach.	x	x

* in OUV

Annex 3: Overview and outline of CVI workshops

Phase 1: 10-11 February 2020, Hamburg, Germany

Plenary sessions shown in Blue
Room 022/023

Small Group sessions shown in Green
Rooms 022/023, 022/024, 2nd floor room 253

10 February 2020

Working lunch will be available for workshop participants from 12:00-12:45, room 022/024

Day 1: 10 February 12:45 – 17:30

1. Overview of workshop aims, introductions, use of plenary and small-group sessions, logistics (toilets, coffee-breaks, etc.)

AIM 1: Understand the Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) framework and its application in the Wadden Sea

2. Provide overview of CVI concept, followed by discussion - presentation

AIM 2: Understand the significant values that comprise the OUV for the Wadden Sea; and assess condition and trend. Discuss other significant values (i.e., Significant Local Values, SLVs)

3. Ensure all participants are aware of the Statement of OUV for the Wadden Sea and how the table of key values was derived from the Statement of OUV - interactive

4. Undertake high-level assessment of current condition (with context of condition at the date of inscription) and recent trend - interactive

5. Discuss other values that are significant at a local/regional scale (i.e., SLVs) but not part of OUV – interactive

AIM 3: Understand future climate change scenarios facing the Wadden Sea

6. Provide overview of climate change scenarios, differences in projected impacts from scenarios including timescales, and geographically-specific projections - presentation

AIM 4: Assess the climate stressors impacting the values of the Wadden Sea and select key climate stressors

7. Show list of climate stressors – check for (i) understanding? (ii) timescales? Do example together of brainstorming top three climate stressors impacting ONE key value (discussed in #3) - presentation

8. Using the list of climate stressors provided, ask small groups to brainstorm what are the top three climate stressors impacting the key values of OUV - interactive

Day 1: 10 February 18:30

Meet for drinks and invited dinner (dinner at 19:30)

11 February 2020

Day 2 morning 09:00 – 12:30

9. Bring outputs from 8. back to plenary and ensure all participants agree on which climate change drivers are impacting the attributes of OUV - interactive

AIM 5: Evaluate vulnerability of OUV to key climate stressors, considering exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity for selected climate scenario (e.g., 'Business as Usual', 'Paris Agreement').

10. Revisit process, including detail of thresholds, for exposure and sensitivity. Review the potential impact matrix that combines these. Revisit process for adaptive capacity and review the OUV Vulnerability matrix that combines these - presentation

11. Participants in groups assess the exposure and sensitivity (thus determining potential impact) and adaptive capacity (thus determining OUV vulnerability) for the key CC drivers. Analyse one agreed scenario e.g. 'Business as Usual' - interactive

12. Bring outputs from 11. back to plenary and discuss any variation in assessments of exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity, and any effect on OUV vulnerability.

Lunch 12:30 – 13:30

Day 2 afternoon 13:30 – latest 16:00

AIM 6: Summary, feedback and next steps - interactive

13. Summarise outcomes from workshop, following final analysis worksheet - interactive

14. Recap on those items that had been 'parked' during the workshop.

15. Introduce Community Vulnerability process for subsequent workshop/s.

16. Short brainstorming community vulnerability

17. Receive feedback on CVI framework and workshop process.

18. Conduct workshop evaluations; other feedback from participants.

Phase 2: Workshop agenda, 16-17 February 2021

Plenary sessions shown in Blue

Breakout Group sessions shown in Green

Pre-workshop viewing (pre-recorded videos)

AIM 1: Ensure all participants understand the Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) framework and how the OUV Vulnerability was derived at the previous workshop

- a) Brief overview of CVI framework
- b) Recap on previous CVI workshop (Feb 2019) – results up to the assessment of OUV Vulnerability
- c) Outline ESC workshop, including outline of scenario for ESC analysis

16 February 2021

Day 1: Live interactive via Zoom, 8:30am-12nn

1. Overview of workshop aims, introductions, use of plenary and small-group sessions, logistics (breaks, etc.)

2. Introductions of participants

AIM 2: Ensure participants understand the scenario to be used during remainder of the CVI assessment

3. Review 2050 scenario for use in ESC discussion (using same timescale(s) as OUV workshop)
 - a) Sea level rise
 - b) Sea temperature trend
 - c) Extreme temperature events

4. Outline process for analysing economic, social and cultural dependency, including the socio-economic potential impact matrix that combines these.

AIM 3: Consider economic dependency (sensitivity) and adaptive capacity as part of Community Vulnerability.

5. Overview of sectors directly dependent upon World Heritage property - interactive (~20 min)

- Description/scope of sector
- Current economic (market) valuation/s (estimate or range)
- Potential climate impacts (from top-three and then others)
- Contributors to this info

Shipping/harbours; Energy/infra-structure; Coastal protection; Tourism; Agriculture; Fishery.

6. Outline process for analysing economic dependency and adaptive capacity

7. Participants in **breakout groups** assess the economic dependency upon the property (thus determining socio-economic potential impact)

- Potential relative change in economic (market) valuation in the scenario described
- Level of dependency upon property

Participants in **breakout groups** then assess the economic adaptive capacity

8. Reconvene in plenary - bring outputs from #7 back to plenary and discuss assessments of economic dependency and adaptive capacity; and implications for social and cultural considerations

- Potential relative change in economic (market) valuation
- Level of dependency upon property
- Interactions with other sectors

9. Process to prepare for Day 2 of workshop

17 February 2021

Day 2: Live interactive via Zoom, 8:30am-12:30pm

10. Recap on Day 1 of workshop (including re-visit 2050 scenario being used); outline of Day 2

- Mentimeter poll

AIM 4: Consider social and cultural dependencies (sensitivity) and adaptive capacity to determine Community Vulnerability.

11. Revisit process for analysing social and cultural dependency and adaptive capacity

- Mentimeter for social aspects
- Mentimeter for cultural aspects

12. Participants in **breakout groups** assess (i) the **social** dependency and then (ii) the **social** adaptive capacity

13. Participants in **breakout groups** assess (i) the **cultural** dependency and then the **cultural** adaptive capacity

14. Bring outputs from #12 & #13 back to plenary and discuss any variation in assessments of adaptive capacity. Examine effect of these on Community Vulnerability. Potential actions/recommendations for future planning.

AIM 5: Summary, feedback and next steps.

15. Summarise outcomes from workshop, following final analysis worksheet

16. Recap on any items that had been 'parked' during the workshop

17. Where to next? Receive feedback on CVI framework and workshop process

Annex 4: List of participating institutions in the CVI Wadden Sea workshops

Institution	Country	Phase 1	Phase 2
Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)	D	x	
ARC Centre for Coral Reef Studies, JCU *	AU	x	x
BfN - Federal Agency for Nature Conservation	D	x	x
Christian-Albrechts-University Kiel	D	x	
CWSS *	trilateral	x	x
Deltares	NL	x	
Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology (SOVON)	NL	x	
Environmental authority of the free Hanseatic city of Hamburg (BUE), National Park Administration Hamburg	D	x	
Fachhochschule Westküste	D		x
Farmers Union and Chamber of Agriculture	D		x
Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU)	D		x
Insel- und Halligkonferenz e.V.	D		x
Institute for Geography, University of Hamburg	D		x
Institute for Tourism Research in Northern Europe (NIT)	D		x
Institute of Coastal Research at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht	D	x	
James Cook University (JCU) *	AU	x	x
Kreis Dithmarschen	D		x
Landwirtschaftskammer Niedersachsen	D		x
Lower Saxon Wadden Sea National Park Authority	D	x	x
Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality	NL	x	x
Ministry of Energy, Agriculture, the Environment, Nature and Digitalization Schleswig-Holstein	D	x	x
Ministry of Environment and Food, Danish Coastal Authority	DK	x	
Ministry of Environment and Food, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)	DK	x	
Nordfriisk Instituut	D		x
Programma naar een Rijke Waddenzee (PRW)	NL	x	x
Rijkswaterstaat *	NL	x	x
Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ)/Waddenacademie	NL	x	x
Schleswig-Holstein Agency for Coastal Defense, National Park and Marine Conservation National Park Authority /Multimar	D	x	x
Senckenberg Research Institute - Marine Research	D	x	
Thünen Institute of Sea Fisheries	D	x	x

Universität Würzburg	D		x
University of Southern Denmark	DK		x
Wadden Sea Forum	trilateral	x	x
Wadden Sea Forum & Trilateral Wadden Sea Sailing Association (TWSSA)	trilateral		x
Waddenacademie	NL	x	x
Waddenvereniging	NL	x	x
Waddenzee.nl	NL		x
Wageningen University and Research	NL	x	
World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF)	D	x	

*Legend: AU – Australia, D – Germany, DK – Denmark, NL – Netherlands; * – Committee. Participation in both workshops by institution does not necessarily imply the same person.*

Annex 5: Acronyms

AU	Australia
CVI	Climate Vulnerability Index
CWSS	Common Wadden Sea Secretariat
D	Germany
DK	Denmark
EG-C	Expert Group-Climate Change Adaptation
ESC	Economic, Social and Cultural (referring to the components of the Community Vulnerability assessment)
JCU	James Cook University
NL	Netherlands
OUV	Outstanding Universal Value
QSR	Quality Status Report
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
SIMP	The SIMP Integrated Management Plan for ONE Wadden Sea World Heritage
SPVs	Other Significant Property Values
TG-WH	Task Group World Heritage
TWSC	Trilateral Wadden Sea Cooperation
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WSB	Wadden Sea Board